

EVALUATING AI APPROACHES TO TRANSLATE UZBEK AND KARAKALPAK PAREMIAS INTO ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT. The translation of culturally dense units, such as paremiological units present significant challenges for machine translation (MT) systems, especially when dealing with under-resourced languages like Uzbek and Karakalpak. Paremiological units including proverbs, idiomatic expressions, and metaphorical phrases are deeply embedded in the cultural fabric of their source communities. Current AI-driven translation tools often struggle to capture the subtle cultural, historical, and contextual meanings inherent in these expressions. This article evaluates the effectiveness of contemporary MT approaches in rendering Uzbek and Karakalpak paremiological units into English, highlighting their shortcomings and lead to culturally inadequacy or misleading outputs. Drawing on regionally sourced corpora and scholarly works, it also proposes a hybrid workflow that combines machine-driven efficiency with human cultural and linguistic expertise. By examining diverse strategies and methodologies. This study aims at contributing to the ongoing discourse on improving translation quality and cultural fidelity in the context of under-resourced languages.

Keywords: Machine translation, paremiological units, Uzbek, Karakalpak, hybrid workflows, cultural context, AI approaches.

INTRODUCTION

The translation of culturally embedded lexical units, particularly paremiological units, poses unique and persistent challenges in the realm of machine translation. While neural machine translation (NMT) and other AI-based techniques have markedly improved the fluency of translations for major world languages, they often fall short when handling culturally rich and context-specific materials from less-resourced languages such as Uzbek and Karakalpak. These languages possess extensive inventories of proverbs and idioms (*maqollar* and *matallar* in Uzbek, *naqil-maqallar* in Karakalpak) that encapsulate

societal norms, moral principles, and collective memories (Qarshiboyev, 2016; Erkinov, 2018).

Existing MT systems frequently prioritize form over cultural meaning, producing output that may be linguistically coherent but contextually impoverished or even misleading (Kontonatsios, 2013; Зиганшина, 2021). For example, a direct, word-for-word translation of a Karakalpak proverb like “*Miynetsiz ómir - qara kómir*” (literally: “A life without effort is black coal.”), cultural-equivalent rendering would be “A life without hard work is empty and dark.” This Karakalpak proverb compares a life devoid of hard work and perseverance to black coal—something dark, of low worth, or unrefined. In this metaphor, “*miynet*” (effort, labor, or diligence) is presented as the force that brings value, meaning, and brightness to one’s existence. Without it, life remains like “*qara ko‘mir*”—unshaped, dull, and lacking intrinsic worth.

In English, while there may not be a direct one-line proverb with the exact imagery, the sentiment aligns with sayings like “No pain, no gain” or “Without effort, there is no reward.” The challenge for a machine translation system is to recognize that the proverb does not speak about coal literally but uses it as a symbol of worthlessness or unfulfilled potential.

This article evaluates current AI approaches to translating Uzbek and Karakalpak paremiological units into English, considering their linguistic complexity, contextual depth, and cultural significance. It then proposes a hybrid human-machine workflow that integrates cultural expertise to improve translation outcomes.

THE MAIN PART

Paremiological units —proverbs, idioms, riddles, and other set expressions—are inseparable from the cultural identities they represent. Uzbek and Karakalpak paremiological units often reflect pastoral traditions, nomadic heritage, agrarian lifestyles, and strong communal values developed over centuries (Qarshiboyev, 2016; Qurbanbaeva, 2019). For instance, the Uzbek proverb “*Qush uyasida ko‘rganini qiladi*” (“A bird does what it sees in the nest”) is not merely an observation about avian behavior; it communicates the cultural belief that children emulate their parents’ actions and that moral instruction starts at home. Similarly, a Karakalpak expression like “*Birlik bar jerde, tirilik bar*” (“Where there is unity, there is life.”) highlights the communal ethos valued among Karakalpak peoples. Translating these expressions into English demands

more than lexical substitution; it requires an awareness of the cultural and historical contexts that shaped these sayings.

MT systems, however, often rely on statistically derived patterns or neural associations learned from limited parallel corpora, lacking the cultural cognition essential for interpreting metaphorical language. While research on the complexity of paremiological translation is ongoing (Farahani, 2020; Turner, 2015), much less attention has been paid to languages with limited digital resources, such as Uzbek and Karakalpak.

Modern machine translation (MT) systems, including neural machine translation (NMT), have significantly improved fluency and grammatical accuracy. However, they still struggle with the cultural depth of paremiological units. Consider the Uzbek idiomatic phrase *“O‘z aravangni o‘zing tort”* (literally, “Pull your own cart”), which urges individuals to handle their own responsibilities without depending on others. A direct, literal translation into English may simply mention “pulling a cart” without conveying the underlying cultural message of self-reliance and personal accountability.

Similarly, the Karakalpak expression *“Kóp sóz eshekke júk”* (literally, “Many words are a burden to a donkey”) criticizes excessive speech as pointless and unwieldy. While an MT system might provide a literal rendition, it would likely fail to communicate the phrase’s pragmatic function—emphasizing that too much talk is no more useful than an unnecessary load on a beast of burden. This inability to capture underlying values and contextual layers underscores the gap between current machine-generated translations and those that truly reflect the paremiological richness of Uzbek and Karakalpak languages.

The shortcomings of MT in translating Uzbek and Karakalpak paremias stem from several factors:

- Data scarcity. Parallel corpora for Uzbek and Karakalpak are limited. MT models trained primarily on English-centric corpora lack exposure to cultural patterns unique to Central Asian languages (Zubair, 2020; Esplà-Gomis, 2022).
- Cultural embeddedness. Paremiological units rely on cultural knowledge, historical events, moral codes, and geographic references. Without explicit cultural modeling, MT systems misinterpret or omit these layers of meaning (Ebrahimi, 2015; Zhang & Jaamour, 2022).
- Lack of adequacy evaluation metrics. Existing BLEU or TER scores cannot fully capture the cultural adequacy of translations. Evaluating

paremiological translations demands qualitative, human-involved assessments that judge cultural fidelity and interpretive success.

To overcome these challenges, a hybrid workflow is proposed. This approach uses MT systems for initial drafts and human experts for post-editing and cultural adaptation:

- Initial MT Pass. Leverage NMT to produce a first-pass translation, ensuring a baseline target text.
- Human post-editing. Engaging bilingual experts fluent in Uzbek or Karakalpak and English who have cultural literacy. They refine the machine output to ensure the proverb's moral, metaphorical, and contextual meanings are preserved.
- Cultural annotation. Adding explanatory footnotes or parenthetical glosses where needed. This preserves cultural nuances for readers unfamiliar with the source culture (Pareti, 2016; Alkhawaja, 2024).

By combining the speed of MT with human interpretive skills, hybrid models can yield more culturally resonant translations. Over time, iterative feedback can improve MT engines trained on culturally annotated corpora, gradually increasing their sensitivity to paremiological subtleties (Wang, 2024; Cheng, 2024).

Preliminary studies are encouraging. In pilot projects, the use of hybrid models—where machine output is refined by human post-editors—has significantly improved the accuracy and cultural relevance of translations from Uzbek and Karakalpak into English. Comparable approaches have also enhanced comprehension and cultural fidelity when applied to intangible cultural heritage and literary texts (Li & Jiang, 2023; Makrynioti, 2019; Das, 2024).

CONCLUSION

Translating Uzbek and Karakalpak paremiological units into English exemplifies the persistent gap between technological prowess and cultural understanding in MT. While NMT systems can produce coherent sentences, they often fail to convey the cultural depth that defines paremiological units. This shortfall is particularly acute for under-resourced languages where training data and cultural resources are limited.

A hybrid human-machine approach offers a promising solution. By harnessing the computational strength of AI and the cultural insight of human experts, we can move towards translations that respect linguistic nuance and cultural integrity. As MT research progresses, prioritizing cultural embedding, expanding language-specific corpora, and refining evaluation criteria can ensure that the

richness of Uzbek and Karakalpak paremiological units are not lost in translation.

References:

1. Alkhawaja R. (2024). Unveiling the new frontier: ChatGPT-3 Powered Translation for Arabic-English language pairs. *Theory and practice in language studies*. doi:10.17507/tpls.1402.05
2. Cheng L. (2024). Integrating neural MT with cultural tagging for improved literary translation. *Journal of translation technology*. 17(2), 45–63.
3. Cespedes Y. (2020). Beyond the margins of academic education: identifying translation industry training practices through action research. *The International Journal of Translation and Interpreting Research*. doi:10.12807/ti.112201.2020.a07
4. Das S. (2024). Statistical machine translation for Indic languages. doi:10.1017/nlp.2024.26
5. Ebrahimi E., Callison-Burch C., & Dou D. (2015). Bold: Biomedical open language dataset. *Proceedings of the ACL workshop on biomedical NLP*.
6. Erkinov A. (2018). Qoraqalpoq tilidagi maqol va matallarning leksik-struktur xususiyatlari. *Qaraqapaq filologiyasi jurnali*, 2(1), 56–72.
7. Esplà-Gomis M., Etchegoyhen T., & Forcada M.L. (2022). Addressing language scarcity in MT training: the promise of domain adaptation. *Machine Translation Journal*, 36(2), 123–142.
8. Farahani M.V. (2020). Cultural concepts in translation: a case study of proverbs. *Journal of Pragmatics and Translation Studies*, 5(4), 89–102.
9. Fitria T. (2021). Difficulties in translating idioms. *Studies in English language and education*. 8(1), 54–68.
10. Fu Y. (2021). Automatic classification of human translation and machine translation: A Study from the perspective of lexical diversity. doi:10.48550/arxiv.2105.04616
11. Kenny D., & Doherty S. (2014). Statistical machine translation in the translation curriculum: overcoming obstacles and empowering translators. *The interpreter and translator trainer*, 8(2), 276–294.
12. Kontonatsios G. (2013). A comparative evaluation of state-of-the-art machine translation for biomedical terminology. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 46(5), 811–818.
13. Lv H., & Jiang S. (2023). A corpus and computer-assisted translation-based study on English translation of intangible cultural heritage terms. doi:10.3233/faia230197

14. Mahardika R. (2017). Translating cultural expressions. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 6(2), 291–300.
15. Makrynioti M. (2019). Translating cultural metaphors in fiction: A cognitive perspective. *Meta: Translators' Journal*, 64(3), 433–448.
16. Pareti S. (2016). Integrating MT and human post-editing in professional workflows. *International Journal of Language and Communication*, 22(3), 112–128.
17. Qarshiboyev B. (2016). *O'zbek maqollari lug'ati*. Toshkent: O'qituvchi.
18. Qurbanbaeva A. (2019). *Karakalpak proverbial expressions: A cultural linguistic perspective*. Nukus: Karakalpakstan State University Press.
19. Turner E., Moriarty M., & Kiely J. (2015). Intercultural encounters: translating culture-bound elements in texts. *Perspectives in Translation*, 23(4), 662–678.
20. Wang Y. (2024). Research on artificial intelligence machine translation based on BP neural algorithm. *ICST Transactions on scalable information systems*, 4(1). doi:10.4108/eetsis.5075
21. Zhang M., & Jaamour A. (2022). Contextualizing cultural references: A survey on MT of cultural items. *Machine translation review*, 78(4), 45–61.
22. Zasiakin S., & Vakuliuk Y. (2020). Ethical issues of neural machine translation. *Psycholinguistics in a modern world*, 15, 81–83.
23. Zubair M. (2020). A Survey on resource-scarce language MT. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Information Technology and Multimedia*, 9(3), 22–35.
24. Зиганшина И.В. (2021). Проблемы автоматического перевода фразеологизмов. *Вестник Казанского Государственного Университета*, 3(2), 98–107.